

Supplementary Materials for: Japan's 2025 Populist Turn from Outside

This document provides supplementary methodological details, additional statistical analyses, and robustness checks supporting the main chapter.

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(Akkerman / Schulz / Hieda & Zenkyo Japanese adaptation)

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Note. Appendices are organized thematically to facilitate verification of measurement validity, psychological structure, and robustness. Their order does not correspond directly to their first appearance in the main text.

Block I. Measurement Foundations and Sample Information
Appendix A. Populism Scale Items and Conceptual Genealogy
 (Akkerman / Schulz / Hieda & Zenkyo Japanese adaptation)

No	index	Question items	Answer 1	Answer 10
Q16_1	POP1_detached from the public	Politicians quickly become distant from the ordinary people .	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_2	POP2_gap between politicians and the public	The political differences between the elite and the people are larger than the differences among the people.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_3	POP3_not	Politicians aren't actually interested in the opinions of	Strongly	Strongly

	interested	ordinary people like me.	Disagree	Agree
Q16_4	POP4_direct voting	The most important political issues should be ultimately decided by the public through direct voting.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_5	POP5_engage with citizens	The people should be asked whenever important decisions are taken.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_6	POP6_lead in shaping public policy	The people, and not politicians, should make our most important policy decisions.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_7	POP7_similar ideas	Most people in general think in a similar way.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_8	POP8_similar interests	Many ordinary people share the same interests and values.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Q16_9	POP9_homogeneity as Japanese people	Although Japanese people have very different personalities, they all ultimately think in the same way.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree

Appendix B. Sample Characteristics and Demographic Composition

(Gender, age, education)

index	Number of people	Percentage
gender		
male	2268	49.8%
female	2287	50.2%

age		
18-19	306	6.7%
20s	654	14.4%
30s	637	14.0%
40s	687	15.1%
50s	692	15.2%
60s	740	16.2%
70s and older	839	18.4%
education		
Currently enrolled in some educational institution	474	10.4%
Junior high school/high school graduate	1435	31.5%
Vocational/junior college graduate	779	17.1%
4 th -year university graduate or above	1867	41.0%

Appendix C. Sources and Classification of Well-Being Indicators: Developers, Origins, and Categories

Category	Indicator	Developer / Origin	Notes
A. Well-being (WB)	SWLS – Satisfaction With Life Scale	Diener, Emmons, Larsen & Griffin (1985)	Evaluative WB
	PERMA (Positive	Seligman (2011); Butler & Kern (2016)	Experiential/affective WB

Category	Indicator	Developer / Origin	Notes
B. Cultural, Eudaimonic, and Future-oriented Meaning	Emotion, Negative Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, Accomplishment)		
	3DM – Three-Dimensional Meaning	Steger et al. (2023).	Existential meaning (Coherence / Purpose / Significance)
	Mattering	Scarpa, Zopluoglu, and Prilleltensky(2022)	Social visibility/recognition
	Ikigai	Japanese cultural psychology	Unique cultural meaning construct
	Inner-richness orientation	Original scale	Value orientation toward depth, maturity, and psychological richness
	HEMA-R – Eudaimonic Orientation	Veronika Huta (2016)	Pursuit of excellence, meaning, challenge, growth
	Virtue Scale	Original scale	Moral–character strengths; cultural eudaimonia
Hope	Original items (theory-informed; not	Future-directed agency & pathways; existential	

Category	Indicator	Developer / Origin	Notes
C. Transcendent & Religious Values		adapted from existing hope scales)	resource; key WB-depletion factor
	Optimism	Original items (theory-informed; not adapted from existing LOT measures)	Generalized positive expectations; basic future security; distinct from Hope
	VIA Spirituality	Peterson & Seligman (2004)	Transcendence strength; sacred connectedness
	Materialism / Post-materialism	Ronald Inglehart (1977, 2018) (selected and partially modified items; Items are selected and reworded by the author based on Inglehart's value framework; some items are reversed or newly constructed to fit the Japanese survey context.	Materialism / Post-materialism (Survival vs. Self-expression values)
	Religiosity / Secularity	Inglehart (2018) (culturally adapted)	Subjective religious importance / secular orientation
	Sanctity	Haidt & Graham (2007)	Purity/sacredness, moral foundation theory

Note. For the materialist/post-materialist dimension, items are not direct reproductions of World Values Survey instruments but are

selected, rephrased, and partially reconstructed by the author based on Inglehart's theoretical framework.

Appendix D. Policy Preference Items and PCA-Based Ideological Framework

(Question items used for left–right and policy evaluation dimensions)

Policy Attitudes

1. COVID-19 Countermeasures

Do you think the government's policy response to the COVID-19 pandemic to date has been appropriate?

2. National Security and Defense Capabilities

Do you believe that strengthening national security and military/defense capabilities should be emphasized in policy?

3. Economic Growth via Deregulation

Do you believe that economic growth through deregulation and privatization should be emphasized in policy?

4. Social Welfare and Inequality

Do you believe that policies aimed at reducing inequality and expanding social welfare should be emphasized?

5. Political Ethics and Anti-Corruption

Do you believe that political ethics and anti-corruption measures should be emphasized in policy?

6. Infectious Disease Control vs. Economic Activity

Do you believe that the protection of life and health (e.g., infectious disease control) should be prioritized over economic activities in policy?

7. Constitutional Reform

Do you believe that Japan's Constitution should be amended, even if it involves changing existing constitutional principles (e.g., popular sovereignty and fundamental human rights)?

8. Monetary Policy and Economic Reform

Do you believe that fundamental policy changes, such as consumption tax cuts or shifts in monetary policy, should be implemented to address rising prices?

9. Gender Equality and Marital Surnames

Do you believe that policies aiming for gender equality—including the introduction of a selective dual-surname system and the recognition of same-sex marriage—should be implemented?

10. Foreign Policy regarding Global Conflicts

Regarding global conflicts (such as the hostilities in Ukraine and Gaza), do you believe that Japan should support the continuation of military operations in these conflicts?

11. Security Legislation and Collective Self-Defense

Do you believe it was appropriate to enact the Peace and Security Preservation Legislation and partially recognize the right to collective self-defense?

12. Nuclear Energy Policy

Do you believe that nuclear power generation should be maintained and promoted as necessary for economic growth?

13. Economic Growth vs. Social Equity

Do you believe that economic growth should be prioritized, even if it results in a certain increase in economic inequality?

14. Policy on Foreign Nationals (Immigration Policy)

Do you believe that stricter policies regarding the acceptance of foreign nationals and their rights should be emphasized in Japan?

Block II. Psychological Structure: Correlations, Axes, and Party-Level Profiles

Appendix E. Correlation Matrix of Core Well-Being Indicators

(SWLS, PERMA dimensions, 3DM, Mattering, Hope, Optimism)

	SWLS	General_WB	PERMA	PERMA_M	3DM (Composite)	Mattering	PERMA_P	PERMA_E	PERMA_R	PERMA_A	Hope	Optimism
SWLS	1	.815**	.808*	.771**	.730**	.741**	.778**	.667**	.743**	.774**	.677**	.763**
General_WB	.815**	1	.999*	.936**	.813**	.833**	.948**	.901**	.895**	.941**	.729**	.691**
PERMA	.808**	.999**	1	.939**	.813**	.831**	.945**	.904**	.894**	.944**	.725**	.686**
PERMA_M	.771**	.936**	.939*	1	.820**	.813**	.840**	.797**	.771**	.925**	.717**	.646**
3DM (Compos)	.730**	.813**	.813*	.820**	1	.841**	.754**	.679**	.694**	.805**	.766**	.615**

ite)												
Mattering	.741**	.833**	.831*	.813**	.841**	1	.778**	.689**	.750**	.810**	.734**	.626**
PERMA_P	.778**	.948**	.945*	.840**	.754**	.778**	1	.841**	.840**	.848**	.700**	.674**
PERMA_E	.667**	.901**	.904*	.797**	.679**	.689**	.841**	1	.751**	.803**	.602**	.585**
PERMA_R	.743**	.895**	.894*	.771**	.694**	.750**	.840**	.751**	1	.782**	.631**	.616**
PERMA_A	.774**	.941**	.944*	.925**	.805**	.810**	.848**	.803**	.782**	1	.698**	.651**
Hope	.677**	.729**	.725*	.717**	.766**	.734**	.700**	.602**	.631**	.698**	1	.580**
Optimism	.763**	.691**	.686*	.646**	.615**	.626**	.674**	.585**	.616**	.651**	.580**	1

** . Correlations are significant at the 1% level (two-tailed).

* . Correlations are significant at the 5% level (two-tailed).

Appendix F. Positioning of PERMA Dimensions Across Analytical Axes

PERMA Dimension	Analytical Axis	Functional Role in the Model
P (Positive Affect)	Axis A	Affective resources and emotional valence
Negative Affect (Anxiety, Anger, Sadness)	Axis A	Emotional strain and threat sensitivity

PERMA Dimension	Analytical Axis	Functional Role in the Model
M (Meaning)	Axis B	Normative and existential interpretation
E (Engagement)	Background (WB Infrastructure)	Active involvement supporting the overall WB
R (Relationships)	Background (WB Infrastructure)	Human relations
A (Accomplishment)	Background (WB Infrastructure)	Efficacy and performance
PERMA (Composite)	Multi-dimensional WB (Title-level)	Integrated well-being construct
SWLS	Subjective WB (Title-level)	Global evaluative well-being

Note. The multidimensional well-being structure is empirically integrated but analytically disaggregated according to its distinct political–psychological functions. All PERMA components are highly intercorrelated (see Appendix E), indicating that they jointly form a multi-dimensional WB structure, even though only selected dimensions are analytically elevated to axis status.

Appendix G. Party-Level Means and Rank Ordering of Well-Being Indicators

(Descriptive profiles illustrating Axis A: affective well-being)

Party support	N1_anxiety		N2_anger		N3_sadness		Negative emotion		N		P	
LDP	-.018		.018		.050**	[9]	.003		.019		.164**	[3]
Komeito	.004		.070**	[7]	.114**	[4]	.044**	[7]	.073**	[7]	.129**	[6]

Ishin	-.023		.029 [†]	[8]	.051**	[8]	.000		.021		.195**	[2]
DPFP	.063**	[1]	.089**	[4]	.100**	[7]	.076**	[2]	.099**	[3]	.162**	[4]
CDP	-.037*	[6]	.006		.029 [†]	[10]	-.025 [†]	[8]	-.002		.205**	[1]
SDP	.013		.077**	[6]	.110**	[5]	.045**	[6]	.077**	[6]	.143**	[5]
JCP	.037*	[4]	.082**	[5]	.130**	[1]	.066**	[4]	.097**	[4]	.104**	[9]
Reiwa	.047**	[3]	.100**	[2]	.119**	[3]	.073**	[3]	.103**	[2]	.089**	[10]
Hoshutō	0.054**	[2]	.122**	[1]	.128**	[2]	.080**	[1]	.118**	[1]	.124**	[7]
Sanseitō	.035*	[5]	.100**	[2]	.101**	[6]	.053**	[5]	.092**	[5]	.113**	[8]

** . Values are statistically significant at the 1% level (two-tailed).

* . Values are statistically significant at the 5% level (two-tailed).

Note. Numbers in parentheses indicate party-level rankings (reported only for statistically significant results).

Appendix H. Value-Based Resources: Correlation Matrix and Party-Level Profiles (Axis B1–B5)

	B1. Intrinsic Eudaimonic Value Orientation	B2. Social Recognition & Life Anchoring	B3. Ethical Spiritual Orientation	B4. Future-Oriented Agency	B5. Hedonic, Material Orientation
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								(Non-sacralized)					
	PERMA_M (Meaning)	Inner Richness	Virtue	Post-Materialism	EUD	Mattering	Ikigai	Spirituality (VIA)	Hope	Optimism	HE D	Materialism	Material Richness
PERMA_M (Meaning)	1	.676**	.738**	.326**	.660**	.813**	.747**	.717**	.717**	.646**	.544**	.341*	.272**
Inner Richness	.676**	1	.551**	.274**	.481**	.620**	.582**	.515**	.561**	.649**	.424**	.262*	.138**
Virtue	.738**	.551**	1	.431**	.744**	.758**	.686**	.738**	.660**	.539**	.612**	.431*	.218**
Post-Materialism	.326**	.274**	.431**	1	.417**	.305**	.325**	.259**	.317**	.219**	.413**	.552*	.093**
EUD	.660**	.481**	.744**	.417**	1	.651**	.670**	.640**	.627**	.445**	.841**	.429*	.243**
Mattering	.813**	.620**	.758**	.305**	.651**	1	.753**	.727**	.734**	.626**	.544**	.333*	.230**

Ikigai	.747**	.582**	.686**	.325**	.670**	.753**	1	.667**	.804**	.593**	.597**	.342*	.163**
Spirituality (VIA)	.717**	.515**	.738**	.259**	.640**	.727**	.667**	1	.645**	.516**	.481**	.287*	.210**
Hope	.717**	.561**	.660**	.317**	.627**	.734**	.804**	.645**	1	.580**	.541**	.344*	.155**
Optimism	.646**	.649**	.539**	.219**	.445**	.626**	.593**	.516**	.580**	1	.404**	.239*	.245**
HED	.544**	.424**	.612**	.413**	.841**	.544**	.597**	.481**	.541**	.404**	1	.468*	.267**
Materialism	.341**	.262**	.431**	.552**	.429**	.333**	.342**	.287**	.344**	.239**	.468**	1	.272**
Material Richness	.272**	.138**	.218**	.093**	.243**	.230**	.163**	.210**	.155**	.245**	.267**	.272*	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).

Note. Within each value block, correlations among subdimensions are generally high, indicating internally coherent orientations. The hedonic/material block (B5) also shows positive associations with other value domains, suggesting that material well-being is not antagonistic to meaning- or virtue-oriented values. However, correlations between B5 and other blocks are relatively weaker, while the internal correlation between materialism and perceived material abundance remains comparatively strong. This pattern indicates that material orientation constitutes a partially autonomous but non-antagonistic domain within the broader value structure.

Appendix I. Political or Pseudo-Sacralization

(Correlations and party-level patterns; Axis C)

This table reports correlations among religiousness, sacralization, and spirituality (VIA), illustrating the distinction between sacralized moralization (Axis C) and intrinsic ethical–spiritual orientation.

	Religiousness	Sanctity	Spirituality (VIA)
Religiousness (overall index)	1	.568**	.485**
Sanctity	.568**	1	.391**
Spirituality (VIA)	.485**	.391**	1
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).			
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).			

Note. Religiousness and sanctity exhibit a relatively strong mutual association, indicating a shared dimension of political or moral sacralization. By contrast, their correlations with intrinsic, non-sacralized spirituality (VIA) are noticeably weaker. This pattern supports the analytical distinction between Axis C (political sacralization) and Axis B–type intrinsic spiritual resources.

Block III. Supplementary Analyses and Robustness Checks

Appendix J. Supplementary Regression Models of Well-Being and Meaning (Relationships among SWLS, meaning, and related indicators)

Individual-Level Regression Model Predicting Experiential Meaning (PERMA-M) from Evaluative Well-Being (SWLS)

Dependent Variable: Experiential Meaning (PERMA-M)

	Standardized Coefficient (β)	p-value	VIF
SWLS	.768	< .001 **	1.014
Age	.028	.003 **	1.014
Gender	-.008	.411	1.000

R² = .596

Adjusted R² = .595

Model significance: p < .001

N = 4,555

Note. This table reports a forced-entry multiple regression model estimated at the individual level. The dependent variable is experiential meaning (PERMA-M). Standardized coefficients (β) are reported. Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) indicate no multicollinearity. p < .01 (two-tailed).

Appendix K. Negative Affect Components and Populist Attitudes

(Anxiety, anger, sadness)

	N1_anxiety	N2_anger	N3_sadness	negative emotion	N	Ne
Three-Dimensional Composite Populism Index	.128**	.123**	.041**	.065**	.115**	.087**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).

Appendix L. Robustness Analyses: Meaning and Seat Change

Note. This appendix reports supplementary robustness checks examining the relationship between meaning and electoral outcomes.

Appendix M. Party-level Association between Populism and Seat Change

Three-Dimensional Composite Populism Index

Note. Each point represents a political party, plotting its mean populist orientation score against the net change in proportional-representation (PR) seats in the 2025 Upper House election. Parties with a higher populist orientation tend to cluster on the positive side of seat gain, whereas system-

stabilizing or center-left parties exhibit limited or negative PR seat changes.

This figure is presented for descriptive and illustrative purposes only, given the small number of parties. It does not establish causal direction. Rather, it highlights a macro-level alignment between populist orientation and electoral expansion, which aligns with the structural pattern identified in the main analyses.

The figure is based on proportional-representation (PR) seat changes, which more directly reflect party-level support structures; district-level results show substantively similar directional patterns and are therefore not separately visualized.

